

Validation of the Precision Scale Perceptive- Cognitive to People with ASD Diagnostic 'PS-PC-ASD'

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Abstract

Ojea (2023) has published the Precision Scale Perceptivo- Cognitive (PS-PC-ASD), with the aim of determining the diagnosis of people with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), which consists of three main weighted domains: 1) the perceptual-cognitive domain, 2) the social domain, and 3) the practical domain, in order to incorporate the measurement of cognitive neural values, which involve the level of neuropsychological and biological processing of information, from the input of information through perceptual sensory memory to semantic memory and its related episodic memory, as well as the development of interconceptual relationships that develop throughout the processes of information coding through working memory.

In this study, the PS-PC-ASD scale has been validated for a total of N: 346 participants, which is a significantly broad sample, being a highly specific group, of which 112 don't have any specific diagnosis, 140 have a level 1 autism diagnosis, 67 have level 2, and 27 have level 3, as the International Classification of the American Psychiatric Association (APA, 2013).

The comparative data, obtained using a one-way ANOVA test, as well as the subsequent transformation of all direct scores (DS) found in the observation questionnaire into typical scores (Z), were used to construct the three categorical dimensions with typified scores: 1) processing category, 2) social category, and 3) behavioural category, whose typical sum provides a highly accurate analysis of explanatory variance, analysed using stepwise linear regression analysis, in which the three dimensions exhibit significant critical levels explaining the diagnostic data within the three categories (sig: .00).

Finally, the correspondence of the total sum of typical scores found in accordance with the corresponding percentile, in intervals of five, the 50th percentile has corresponded to the typical average sum of -1.38, from which point a diagnosis compatible with autism can be definitively considered. From this percentile onwards, an increase in intensity implies greater severity in the diagnostic group for this disorder.

In essence, the initial data found for the construction of the Scale has been corroborated, concluding that the Diagnostic Precision scale is a highly effective and positive instrument for the specific diagnostic precision of individuals with ASD.

Keywords: *autism spectrum disorder, diagnostic test, perception, cognition, semantic memory, source memory, episodic memory.*

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Introduction

The conceptual review carried out by the 5th International Classification (DSM-5) of the American Psychiatric Association (APA) (2013) categorises the diagnostic group of people with ASD as a multilevel disorder, based on a set of clinical behavioural symptoms, regarding to two basic dimensions: 1) the presence of deficits in social interaction and communication, and 2) stereotyped and restrictive behaviours.

However, scientific research has updated this initial diagnostic basis and incorporated basic assumptions based on cognitive differential components that interact with the social and behavioural symptom group, being both the cause and consequence of these symptoms, however, without observing the neural components, it isn't easy to understand the concept of autistic disorder as a whole.

This perspective enables us to identify alterations in the GABAergic interneuronal process, which functions as the system connecting information across thought and behavioural action in individuals with ASD (Adorjan et al., 2017; Amina et al., 2021; Ariza et al., 2018; Hashemi et al., 2017; Lawrence et al., 2010), which is a set of inhibitory processes that make up 20–30 per cent of all neocortical neurons of many different subtypes, based on differences in cellular morphology, electrophysiology, and circuit connectivity (Zaitsev et al., 2005), whose markers are expressed exclusively in a non-overlapping manner, forming a global network that regulates the activity of local glutamatergic pyramidal projection neurons and, likewise, between them, and actively intervene during the connectivity and flow of information from the moment it is perceived through sensory memory until that same information, if it has managed to pass through the connectional process, can be retrieved from permanent memory in order to establish a new relationship with other new perceived stimulus, or rather, apply it in a practical behavioural setting (DeFelipe et al., 2013; Hof et al., 1999).

Neural deficits affecting cortical connectivity are systemically correlated with social behaviours and specific observable behaviours in individuals with ASD, owing, precisely, to the high systemicity of brain interneuronal functioning, above all with regard to three brain regions linked to the prefrontal cortex (BA9, 46 y 47), whose functionality directly affects circuit connectivity and the highly specific function of the neocortex, which ends up having a significant impact on the development of relationships to personal activity of the relevant behavioural functions of people with ASD (Wang et al., 2016); Precisely because of the highly related cortical functions, as complex cognitive abilities (Ariza et al., 2018, *op. cit.*; Snow, 2016), language and cognition (Hertrich et al., 2021), cognitive-emotional behavioural control (Tanji & Hoshi, 2008) and social and emotional behaviour (Beer et al., 2006).

In this regard, Fatemi et al. (2009) demonstrated that deficits in information connectivity may provide the primary basis for diagnosing this disorder, affecting all components involved in neuropsychological information processing, as evidenced by highly significant reductions in protein levels in the GABA-A and GABA-B receptor subunits, belonging to the superior frontal cortex, parietal cortex, and cerebellum, it seems evident there is a significant reduction in the protein complex of GABA receptors, especially in the GABA-A subunit. This results in GABAergic brain connectivity dysfunction, which affects the fluidity of input-output information processing and stimulus recovery-input, especially when these are more complex and/or requiring the functioning of higher basic psychological processes, owing, among other reasons, to the GABA-A receptors being ionic circuits responsible for mediating behavioural inhibition (Ma et al. 2005). For this purpose, alterations in perception, cognition, and memory are basic values that should be included in the overall assessment of the disorder.

The diagnosis specificity of the disorder has been officially classified into three levels of intensity, in relation to the human and technological support needs and support types

required by these individuals in receiving a psychoeducational proposal adapted to their specific characteristics, going from light needs (level 1) to specific needs requiring more in-depth support (level 3). However, this doesn't mean that levels of intensity, relating to degrees and kinds of help, can be labelled with high precision, on the other hand, the three levels of severity combine with each other throughout multiple sequences of intensity in one dimension or another, giving rise to a specific heterogeneity in each specific situation.

McQuaid et al. (2021) assert that the knowledge and training of diagnostic specialists in relation to developmental functioning is a fundamental aspect of the validity and reliability of diagnosis, since it is the degree of functional adaptability of the personal perceptual-cognitive system to the context and the developmental progress of basic human skills that generally allows for the initial differentiation of a specific differential process, which correlated with both daily living skills and interpersonal and communication skills, such that any alteration in one or more areas will allow the detection of potential indicators of a differential diagnostic process, in terms of statistical probability, which must then be corroborated through analysis of all areas of the perceptual-cognitive processing system (Carter et al., 1998; Howlin et al., 2013; Kanne et al., 2011; Kraijer, 2000; Matson & Shoemaker, 2009). Gaigg et al. (2008) observed greater processing of local and individual elements throughout the learning process in individuals with ASD, owing to a perceived deficit in processing relational elements, leading to greater difficulties in information retrieving when it depends on divergent conceptual categorical relationships, although these same deficits are not found when analysing characteristics that are very local or highly related to a well-assimilated conceptual category, even at the semantic level.

People with ASD show very limited abilities to incorporate episodic context or source memory, which related to the self-other context, within the socio-personal space-time environment experienced throughout learning (Bowler et al., 2000; Bowler et al., 2007; Lind & Bowler, 2009), which will give rise to deficits in the processing connectivity of the relationships between

previously learned elements and new input concepts, as well as the relationship between interconnected concepts and/or actions. Above all, if it is a question of relating fairly infrequent elements or stimuli from a particular conceptual category, they may be stored in an erroneous semantic category and subsequently retrieved from an erroneous semantic category, meaning the answer to the question will also be wrong. Therefore, it is essential to know whether a person with ASD, when they retrieve a word or a simple concept, does so in a phonological way, i.e., because it sounds linguistically familiar to him/her, or in the sense of the concept's meaning, because if this is no longer this situation, the development of information connections becomes greatly complicated, systemically limiting the entire processing system. The learning context will facilitate the construction of semantic criteria, which enable greater learning development and behavioural adaptation to contexts. Therefore, working with perceptual contexts is the key basis for the ongoing development of people with ASD, beginning at an early age, with any necessary adaptations based on each individual's specific needs.

All these findings have recently been investigated directly, confirming that there's high connectivity between the cerebellum and regions of the cortex in people with ASD (Igelström et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2015; Oldehinkel et al., 2019), which highlight the cortical relationships specific to this diagnostic group; more specifically, Khan et al. (2015) have divided the cortex in regions primarily engaged in sensory-motor or supramodal functions, which means, in higher-order cognitive areas and examined the functional connectivity between regions of the cortex and cerebellum in children and adolescents aged 8 to 17 years. They found the cerebellum exhibited hyperconnectivity with the cortex sensorimotor regions and, nevertheless, high hypoconnectivity with supramodal regions in people with ASD. Likewise, in people with ASD, an increase in connections between the supramodal regions of the cerebellum and the sensorimotor regions of the cortex was observed and backwards.

Furthermore, Igelström et al. (2017) divided the temporoparietal union, an important region in social cognition, in 11 subdivisions through independent component analysis. These subdivisions were used as seeds to examine functional connectivity with cerebellar voxels, and a decrease in functional connectivity was observed in children and adolescents with ASD.

Similarly, a recent study by Olivito et al. (2016) found decreased functional connectivity at resting state between the left cerebellar dentate nucleus and cortical regions that are involved in theory of mind and resting-state networks in adults with ASD. In fact, they detected hyperconnectivity between the left dentate nucleus and cerebellar supramodal regions in ASD.

Another study observed a decrease in grey matter volume in the right Crus II in individuals with ASD and also found decreased connectivity in ASD between the right Crus II and the frontal, temporal, and parietal regions.

In overall, several studies have reported limited and sometimes obstructed connectivity in individuals with ASD between the cerebellum and cortical regions that are involved in the execution of higher-order supramodal functions (Olivito et al., 2017), consequently, numerous previous studies have provided evidence of altered cerebellar-cerebral connectivity and suggesting the connectivity between the cerebellum and the supramodal regions of the cortex is of special relevance. Nevertheless, few studies have investigated cerebellar connectivity with supramodal cortical networks, such as intrinsic connectivity networks (Menon, 2011), but, in essence, the results are contributing to a new and constantly growing field of study on cerebellar-cerebral connectivity in this disorder, specifically between the ventromedial default neural network and the left lobes I-IV.

Long-distance hypoconnectivity in people with ASD means that any aspect of psychological function that requires coordination or integration between brain regions is susceptible to disruption, particularly when the computational workload required for such coordination is very high (Just et al., 2004), that deficits in social interaction, language, and

repetitive and restrictive behaviours developed owing these're the domains that set the highest demands on the temporal integration of information sourced from brain areas (Herbert, 2005; Lewis et al., 2006). As such, this theory is, in a way, a neural basis for the theory of central coherence (Happé, 1999; Happé & Frith, 2006), who argued there is a cognitive style focused on processing local information rather than global information (Happé, 1999), even though, Just et al. (2004) have questioned this, proposing the theory of subconnectivity to explain coherence as an emergent feature of the interaction between brain centres.

Structural connectivity has been assessed through MRI-based techniques, such as diffusion tensor imaging (Behrens et al., 2003; Karlsgodt et al., 2008), who examined the structural integrity of white substance tracts, considered to be interareal macrostructural correlates of brain connectivity, which has been corroborated by many other studies (Fields, 2008; Oishi et al., 2008; Karadottir et al., 2008; Schummers, Yu & Sur, 2008; Ziskin et al., 2007).

Likewise, tractography (Hagmann et al., 2003; Hagmann et al., 2008; Lewis et al., 2009) allowed to identify fiber tracts, enabling to map association fibre pathways in the living organism, which explained the deficits in connectivity. However, these techniques present some problems, particularly, when dealing with the multiple orientations of fibres within the same voxel (Wedeen et al., 2008).

The PS-PC-ASD (Ojea, 2023, *op. cit.*) was, therefore, based on the analysis of perceptual-cognitive, social and behavioural factors and dimensions, which were observed through the activities and methodology indicated in the original Scale booklet, which is structured on the basis of five dimensions of observation:

- I) Perception of information.
- II) Encoding of information.
- III) Development of relationships-nodes.
- IV) Memory and recovery.
- V) Fiction and imagination.

Based on the study of these five conceptual dimensions, perceptual-cognitive concepts, semantic and episodic memory were integrated, which are related to symbolic attribution, fiction and imagination, social and behavioural processes, and specific stereotypical and restrictive behaviours.

The data observed were noted throughout the quantitative observation process, from 0 (no disorder) to 4 (very high disorder), regarding to ten variables-factors, which precisely analyse the five components mentioned above, corresponding to three categorical dimensions (see Table 1): I) the processing category, which includes the calculated factors from 1 to 6, II) the social category, which is shaped by factors 6 and 7; and III) the behaviour category, which is a weighted sum of factors 9 and 10.

Table 1. Factors and Their Respective Categories

Categories	Factors Observation
Category: Processing/6	1. Understanding conceptual units.
	2. Reconstruction of significant.
	3. Hierarchisation of categories.
	4. Development of conceptual node relationships.
	5. Development of categorical node relationships.
	6. Information recovery.
Category: Social/2	7. Social interaction.
	8. Social communication.
Category: Behaviour/2	9. Stereotypical behaviours.
	10. Restrictive behaviours.

Afterwards, the direct scores (DS) found throughout the observation process were transformed into their corresponding typical scores (ZS) in the aim of working with the standard statistical deviations of each data value, in relation to the statistical sample mean. Likewise, the three dimensional categories have been calculated in a weighted manner, associated with a corresponding percentile, whose final sum

integrates the final data together with the definitive percentiles for the location of the diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder, with the statistical probability of a positive diagnosis of this disorder starting at the 50th percentile.

Study Objectives

the initial data from the construction of the Perceptual - Behavioural Precision Scale (PS-PC-ASD) for the diagnosis of individuals with ASD (Ojea, 2023, *op. cit.*), using a much larger sample of participants, N: 346, including students and individuals with and without autism, currently corresponding to the three of ASD.

Methodology

Research Design

The design of this study is founded on a quantitative analysis of the observation based on the questionnaire of the above-mentioned Scale. Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis is significantly high ($\alpha = .91$), which led to the conclusion that study is highly reliable.

The main analyses are based, first, on one-way ANOVA, in the aim of explaining the behaviour of the dynamic variables, which include the three categories of the study, regarding to the variables 'group,' 'gender,' and 'age' of the participants.

Lastly, the raw scores are converted into their corresponding standardised values to continue with the study, which concludes with the identification of each student's Z score with their corresponding percentile (P) for the diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder.

Participants

A total of 346 participants were involved in this study. According the variable 'group' (diagnosis way), this corresponds to 112 students with no specific diagnosis; 140 diagnosed with ASD-1; 67 diagnosed with ASD-2, and 27 students diagnosed with ASD-3, whose features by age and gender can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Participants Based on ‘Group’ and ‘Age’ and ‘Gender’ (N: 346)

Gender			Age					Total
			3-6.9	7-10.9	11-13.9	14-17.9	>18	
Men	Group	NO ASD	5	29	28	3	19	84
		ASD-1	4	68	25	9	3	109
		ASD-2	9	14	7	8	9	47
		ASDS-3	0	3	5	6	0	14
	Total		18	114	65	26	31	254
Women	Group	NO ASD	0	4	20	4	0	28
		ASD-1	3	18	6	4	0	31
		ASD-2	4	8	3	2	3	20
		ASD-3	7	1	5	0	0	13
	Total		14	31	34	10	3	92

Variables

The study variables are grouped into 13 variables, 3 fixed variables and 10 factors.

The fixed variables were made up of the following variables: 1) ‘group,’ corresponding to the codes: 0: no ASD; 1: ASD-1, 2) ASD-2 and 3) ASD-3. The variable ‘gender,’ corresponding to the codes: 0: men, and 1: women. Finally, the variable ‘age,’ whose codes were as follows: 0: 3-6 years, 1: 7-10 years, 2: 11-13 years, 3: 14-17.0 years and 3: >18 years.

Factors are distributed among three categories: I) the PROCESSING category, with six variables: 1) ‘concepts,’ 2) ‘meanings,’ 3) ‘hierarchisation,’ 4) ‘interconcepts,’ 5) ‘nodes,’ and 6) ‘retrieval’; II) the SOCIAL category, consisting of two variables: 7) ‘interaction,’ and 8) ‘social behaviour’; and III) the BEHAVIOUR category, consisting of two other variables: 9) ‘stereotypies,’ and 10) ‘restriction.’

The initial values observed constitute the direct scores (DS) for each variable, which, for greater statistical precision, have subsequently been transformed into their corresponding typical scores (ZS).

The base of the ZS has been formed by the corresponding means for the statistical calculation of the three study categories, whose configuration corresponds to the sum of the dynamic variables divided by number of variables that each category comprises.

The three categories formed by the ZS have been transformed into the sum of total ZS in aim

of locating the definitive percentile (P) to determine the ASD’ final diagnostic.

Data Analysis

Data found has been processed through the following statistical analyses. The comparative descriptive study of the behaviour of the different variables-items, initial dynamic predictors of the study regarding to the study's passive personal variables, through a one-way ANOVA analysis, as well as the corresponding test of homogeneity of the analysed variance.

Afterwards, the SD of the factors were transformed to their corresponding ZS for greater study' statistical reliability, as well as the clustering of the corresponding means for all factors, categorized by both SD and their Z-equivalents.

Once the Z values were found, a stepwise regression analysis was performed for the whole set of study variables, enabling the steps included in the analysis to be defined in predicting the most significant predictor variables for the diagnosis.

In the following section, the categorical means have been found, that is, the three corresponding categories with their PDs and their equivalent Z-scores, related to the corresponding percentile, whose purpose is to determine the greater or lesser impact that a given category has on the final summative diagnosis process.

At last, the final sum was determined, both for SD and ZS, to precisely determine the frequency

analysis established in percentiles constructed in intervals of five.

With this previous process, all that is left to do is enter the data requested in Table 15 to complete the ASD diagnostic process.

Procedure

The PS-PC-ASD was applied to the sample of participants, followed by the indicators and activities developed in the initial scale, with the same activities and procedures indicated in this scale (Ojea, 2023, *op. cit.*), whose analysis was adjusted in accordance with ethical principles and the corresponding permissions from the students' families.

Results

Firstly, the level of significance of the incidence of each factor was observed regarding the variables “group”, “gender” and “age” as part of a one-way ANOVA test.

In regard to the variable ‘group,’ Table 3 shows that all variables indicate significant differential values in relationship to the dependent variable (DV) ‘group’ (sig: .00), Therefore, it can be stated that the mean values for the samples are equal, i.e. the dynamic variables don't have a different DV and, consequently, the factors are independent of the DV, significantly contributing to and explaining their differences found.

Table 3. ANOVA to “Group” Variable

Factors		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Concepts	Between-groups	112.13	3	37.37	37.13	.00
	Within-groups	344.24	342	1.00		
	Total	456.38	345			
Meanings	Between-groups	107.07	3	35.69	43.48	.00
	Within-groups	280.67	342	.82		
	Total	387.74	345			
Hierarchisation	Between-groups	113.15	3	37.72	46.30	.00
	Within-groups	278.58	342	.81		
	Total	391.74	345			
Interconcepts	Between-groups	127.31	3	42.43	67.81	.00
	Within-groups	214.02	342	.62		
	Total	341.34	345			
Nodes	Between-groups	105.78	3	35.26	51.40	.00
	Within-groups	234.57	342	.68		
	Total	340.35	345			
Retrieval	Between-groups	106.65	3	35.55	42.98	.00
	Within-groups	282.86	342	.82		
	Total	389.51	345			
Interaction	Between-groups	167.41	3	55.80	134.21	.00
	Within-groups	142.19	342	.41		
	Total	309.61	345			
Social Communication	Between-groups	231.52	3	77.17	118.22	.00
	Within-groups	223.24	342	.65		
	Total	454.76	345			
Stereotypies	Between-groups	341.24	3	113.74	120.69	.00
	Within-groups	322.32	342	.94		
	Total	663.57	345			
Restriction	Between-groups	286.75	3	95.58	88.43	.00
	Within-groups	369.66	342	1.08		
	Total	656.41	345			

The ‘gender’ variable was analysed in the same way. The sample for this variable includes 254

men and 92 women. However, in this situation, the data differ, as there're justly similar sample

sizes in the variables 'concepts' (sig: .01), "interconcepts" (sig: .00) and 'recovery' (sig: .00), whereas, in all other variables the mean is different regarding the variable 'gender', as they

don't indicated significant critical values, and therefore, an explanatory variance of the other factors regarding the variable 'gender' can't be explained (see Table 4).

Table 4. ANOVA to "Gender" Variable

Factors		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Concepts	Between-groups	7.31	1	7.31	5.60	.01
	Within-groups	449.06	344	1.30		
	Total	456.38	345			
Meanings	Between-groups	1.86	1	1.86	1.66	.19
	Within-groups	385.88	344	1.12		
	Total	387.74	345			
Hierarchisation	Between-groups	2.58	1	2.58	2.28	.13
	Within-groups	389.15	344	1.13		
	Total	391.74	345			
Interconcepts	Between-groups	9.49	1	9.49	9.83	.00
	Within-groups	331.85	344	.96		
	Total	341.34	345			
Nodes	Between-groups	2.18	1	2.18	2.21	.13
	Within-groups	338.17	344	.98		
	Total	340.35	345			
Retrieval	Between-groups	14.09	1	14.09	12.91	.00
	Within-groups	375.42	344	1.09		
	Total	389.51	345			
Interaction	Between-groups	2.44	1	2.44	2.73	.09
	Within-groups	307.16	344	.89		
	Total	309.61	345			
Social Communication	Between-groups	.80	1	.80	.61	.43
	Within-groups	453.95	344	1.32		
	Total	454.76	345			
Stereotypies	Between-groups	.10	1	.10	.05	.81
	Within-groups	663.46	344	1.92		
	Total	663.57	345			
Restriction	Between-groups	.00	1	.00	.00	.98
	Within-groups	656.41	344	1.90		
	Total	656.41	345			

However, in the ANOVA comparison level of one factor for the variable 'group,' the descriptive level of the DV, regarding the 'age' variable all age-intervals, including 32 students aged 3 to 6.9 years, 145 students aged 7 to 10.9

years, 99 between 11 and 13.9 years old, 36 students in the age range of 14 to 17.9, and finally, 34 people over 18 years old, showed significant critical levels to all the study' dynamic variables (see Table 5).

Table 5. ANOVA to "Age" Variable

Factors		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Concepts	Between-groups	44.46	4	11.11	9.20	.00
	Within-groups	411.91	341	1.20		
	Total	456.38	345			
Meanings	Between-groups	31.27	4	7.81	7.47	.00

	Within-groups	356.47	341	1.04		
	Total	387.74	345			
Hierarchisation	Between-groups	21.25	4	5.31	4.89	.00
	Within-groups	370.49	341	1.08		
	Total	391.74	345			
Interconcepts	Between-groups	22.53	4	5.63	6.02	.00
	Within-groups	318.80	341	.93		
	Total	341.34	345			
Nodes	Between-groups	18.05	4	4.51	4.77	.00
	Within-groups	322.30	341	.94		
	Total	340.35	345			
Retrieval	Between-groups	40.40	4	10.10	9.86	.00
	Within-groups	349.11	341	1.02		
	Total	389.51	345			
Interaction	Between-groups	20.38	4	5.09	6.00	.00
	Within-groups	289.22	341	.84		
	Total	309.61	345			
Social Communication	Between-groups	49.78	4	12.44	10.48	.00
	Within-groups	404.98	341	1.18		
	Total	454.76	345			
Stereotypies	Between-groups	44,83	4	11.20	6.17	.00
	Within-groups	618.73	341	1.81		
	Total	663.57	345			
Restriction	Between-groups	56.23	4	14.05	7.98	.00
	Within-groups	600.18	341	1.76		
	Total	656.41	345			

For the comparative ANOVA one-factor study as a whole, it can be seen the hypothesis of equality of variances can be rejected, which has been analysed through Levene's test. As can be seen in Table 6, this equality can be rejected in all the variables that form the processing and social category. However, the factors that form

the behaviour category: 'stereotypies' and, very slightly, also the factor 'restriction' factor, which was on the limit of significant; therefore, in these two factors, the hypothesis of equality could not be rejected, as their critical levels indicated equality of variances with respect to the factor 'group'.

Table 6. Test of Homogeneity of Variances

Factors	Leven statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Concepts	35.00	3	342	.00
Meanings	25.39	3	342	.00
Hierarchisation	33.30	3	342	.00
Interconcepts	67.99	3	342	.00
Nodes	12.17	3	342	.00
Retrieval	56.92	3	342	.00
Interaction	12.65	3	342	.00
Social Communication	5.19	3	342	.00
Stereotypies	1.42	3	342	.23
Restriction	2.55	3	342	.05

In the interest of working with more statistically reliable data, each DS for each item-factor corresponding to the three categories has been transformed into its corresponding ZS, which will determine the probability of a specific

diagnosis of this disorder (see Tables 7abc). In this respect, each evaluator can quantify their direct observation with each typical reference score, which can provide them with information

about the strengths and weaknesses regarding the ASD' final diagnosis.

Table 7a. Transformation of the DS to ZS to Processing Category

Processing Category (6)												
P	Conce pts	Zconc epts	meani ngs	Zmeani ngs	hierar chi	Zhiera rchi	interc onc	Zinterc onc	nod es	Zno des	retrie val	Zretri eval
5	,00	-2,05	1,00	-1,24	1,00	-1,24	1,00	-1,44	1,00	-1,53	1,00	-1,60
10	1,00	-1,18	1,00	-1,24	1,00	-1,24	1,00	-1,44	1,00	-1,53	1,00	-1,60
15	1,00	-1,18	1,00	-1,24	1,00	-1,24	1,00	-1,44	2,00	-,52	2,00	-,66
20	1,00	-1,18	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,44	2,00	-,52	2,00	-,66
25	2,00	-,31	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,44	2,00	-,52	2,00	-,66
30	2,00	-,31	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,44	2,00	-,52	2,00	-,66
35	2,00	-,31	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,44	2,00	-,52	2,00	-,66
40	2,00	-,31	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,44	2,00	-,52	2,00	-,66
45	2,00	-,31	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,44	2,00	-,52	2,00	-,66
50	2,00	-,31	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,44	2,00	-,52	2,00	-,66
55	2,00	-,31	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,44	2,00	-,52	3,00	,27
60	2,00	-,31	2,00	-,30	2,00	-,30	3,00	,56	3,00	,48	3,00	,27
65	3,00	,55	3,00	,63	3,00	,63	3,00	,56	3,00	,48	3,55	,79
70	3,00	,55	3,00	,63	3,00	,63	3,00	,56	3,00	,48	4,00	1,2
75	3,00	,55	3,00	,63	3,00	,63	3,00	,56	3,00	,48	4,00	1,21
80	4,00	1,41	3,00	,63	3,00	,63	3,60	1,16	4,00	1,48	4,00	1,21
85	4,00	1,41	4,00	1,52	4,00	1,57	4,00	1,56	4,00	1,48	4,00	1,21
90	4,00	1,41	4,00	1,58	4,00	1,57	4,00	1,56	4,00	1,48	4,00	1,21
95	4,00	1,41	4,00	1,58	4,00	1,57	4,00	1,56	4,00	1,48	4,00	1,21
100	4,00	1,41	4,00	1,58	4,00	1,57	4,00	1,56	4,00	1,48	4,00	1,21

Table 7b. Transformation of the DS a ZS to Social Category

P	Social Category (2)			
	Interaction	Zinteraction	social communic	Zsocial communic
5	2.16	-1.22	1.97	-1.71
10	1.00	-1.22	.00	-1.71
15	1.00	-1.22	.00	-.84
20	1.00	-1.22	1.00	-.84
25	1.00	-.17	1.00	-.84
30	2.00	-.17	1.00	-.84
35	2.00	-.17	1.00	.02
40	2.00	-.17	2.00	.02
45	2.00	-.17	2.00	.02
50	2.00	-.17	2.00	.02
55	2.00	-.17	2.00	.02
60	2.00	-.17	2.00	.02
65	2.00	-.17	2.00	.02
70	2.00	-.17	2.00	.02
75	2.00	-.17	2.00	.02
80	2.00	.88	2.00	.89
85	3.00	1.93	3.00	1.76
90	4.00	1.93	4.00	1.76
95	4.00	1.93	400	1.76
100	4.00	1.93	4.00	1.76

Table 7c. Transformation of the DS a ZS to Behaviour Category

p	BEHAVIOUR CATEGORY (2)			
	stereotypies	Zstereotypies	restricction	Zrestriction
5	1.84	-1.32	1.77	-1.28
10	.00	-1.32	.00	-1.28
15	.00	-1.32	.00	-1.28
20	.00	-1.32	.00	-1.28
25	.00	-1.32	.00	-1.28
30	.00	-.60	.00	-.56
35	1.00	.11	1.00	-.56
40	2.00	.11	1.00	.16
45	2.00	.11	2.00	.16
50	2.00	.11	2.00	.16
55	2.00	.11	2.00	.16
60	2.00	.11	2.00	.16
65	2.00	.11	2.00	.16
70	2.00	.11	2.00	.16
75	2.00	.83	2.00	.16
80	3.00	.83	2.00	.88
85	3.00	1.55	3.00	1.61
90	4.00	1.55	4.00	1.61
95	4.00	1.55	4.00	1.61
100	4.00	1.55	4.00	3.06

As a follow-up to the above scores, it's possible sum the grouping of the DS arithmetic means regarding to the grouped ZS means, likewise

distributed for the three categories, based on the 'group' variable, as can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Means (μ) Grouped, Equivalent between the μ DS y μ ZS

Categories	Dinamic Variables	Group	N	μ DS	μ ZS
Processing	Concepts	NO ASD	112	2.11	-.22
		ASD-1	140	2.00	-.31
		ASD-2	67	2.96	.51
		ASD-3	27	3.89	1.32
	Meanings	NO ASD	112	1.85	-.48
		ASD-1	140	2.16	-.15
		ASD-2	67	2.88	.52
		ASD-3	27	3.78	1.37
	Hierarchisation	NO ASD	112	1.86	-.43
		ASD-1	140	2.16	-.56
		ASD-2	67	2.81	.45
		ASD-3	27	3.93	1.50
	Interconcepts	NO ASD	112	1.98	-.46
		ASD-1	140	2.19	-.25
		ASD-2	67	3.10	.66
		ASD-3	27	4.00	1.56
	Nodes	NO ASD	112	1.99	-.53
		ASD-1	140	2.41	-.10
		ASD-2	67	3.06	.54
		ASD-3	27	3.93	1.41
Retrieval	NO ASD	112	2.45	-.24	
	ASD-1	140	2.33	-.35	
	ASD-2	67	3.42	.66	
	ASD-3	27	4.00	1.21	
Social	Interaction	NO ASD	112	1.36	-.84

	Social Communication	ASD-1	140	2.18	.02
		ASD-2	67	2.82	.69
		ASD-3	27	3.74	1.66
		NO ASD	112	1.04	-.80
		ASD-1	140	1.94	-.27
		ASD-2	67	2.92	.82
		ASD-3	27	3.62	1.44
Behaviour	Stereotypies	NO ASD	112	.54	-.93
		ASD-1	140	2.06	,.58
		ASD-2	67	2.91	.76
		ASD-3	27	3.40	1.15
	Restriction	NO ASD	112	.54	-.89
		ASD-1	140	2.12	.25
		ASD-2	67	2.46	.49
		ASD-3	27	3.37	1.15

But what is the type of predictive explanation of the factors in relation to the type of diagnosis or variable 'group'? To answer this question, the statistical test of stepwise regression analysis has been applied to all study' dynamic variables.

Table 9 gives a summary of the final model, showing the number of steps needed to build the regression model, which involved four steps. The first step included "interaction" factor, which corresponds to the social category. The second step included the 'restriction' factor, which belongs to the behavioural category. The third and fourth steps included variables corresponding to the processing category: 'interconcepts' (interrelationships) and 'concepts' (perception and sensory memory) factors.

Table 9. Variables Entered^a

Model	Variables entered	Method
1	Interaction	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter <= ,050, Probability-of-F-to-remove >= ,100).
2	Restriction	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter <= ,050, Probability-of-F-to-remove >= ,100).
3	Interconcepts	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter <= ,050, Probability-of-F-to-remove >= ,100).
4	Concepts	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter <= ,050, Probability-of-F-to-remove >= ,100).

Note: a) DV: "group".

The summary of the model (see Table 10) highlights how the level of explanation of the factors is increased throughout the four steps outlined. As such, the 'interaction factor which indicates a corrected R² of .53, increases to .58 in the second step: 'restriction.' Finally, the model increased the corrected R² from .62 and .64 for the procedural factors of 'interconcepts' and 'concepts' respectively belonging to the processing category, thus increasing the explanation of the regression model by 11 points.

Table 10. Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. error of the estimate
1	.733(a)	.538	.536	.62
2	.766(b)	.587	.584	.58
3	.789(c)	.623	.620	.56
4	.805(d)	.649	.645	.54

Note: a) Predictors: (constant), interaction; b) Predictors: (constant), interaction, restriction.; c) Predictors: (constant), interaction, restriction, interconcepts; d) Predictors: (constant), interaction, restriction, interconcepts, concepts.

The ANOVA table showed the value of the F statistic, which analysed the value of R² for each step. As can be seen, all steps indicated significant critical levels, with R² values

significantly different from zero in the four steps included in the regression model (see Table 11).

Table 11. ANOVA(e)

Model		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	154.22	1	154.22	400.28	.00(a)
	Residual	132.54	344	.38		
	Total	286.76	345			
2	Regression	168.24	2	84.12	243.45	.00(b)
	Residual	118.51	343	.34		
	Total	286.76	345			
3	Regression	178.69	3	59.56	188.48	.00(c)
	Residual	108.07	342	.31		
	Total	286.76	345			
4	Regression	186.03	4	46.50	157.43	.00(d)
	Residual	100.73	341	.29		
	Total	286.76	345			

Note: a) Predictors: (constant), interaction; b) Predictors: (constant), interaction, restriction; c) Predictors: (constant), interaction, restriction, interconcepts; d) Predictors: (constant), interaction, restriction, interconcepts, concepts; e) DV: “group”.

The partial regression coefficients corresponding to each of the variables included within the model can be observed, especially the Beta value, which clarifies the importance of

each variable inside the model and the critical level of significant, which is positive for all the steps gathered by the regression model (see Table 12).

Table 12. Coefficients(a)

Model		Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. error	Beta		
1	(constant)	-.50	.08		-6.02	.00
	interaction	.70	.03	.73	20.00	.00
2	(constant)	-.47	.07		-6.00	.00
	interaction	.54	.04	.56	12.86	.00
	restriction	.18	.02	.27	6.37	.00
3	(constant)	-.71	.08		-8.26	.00
	interaction	.39	.04	.41	8.41	.00
	restriction	.19	.02	.29	7.00	.00
	interconcepts	.21	.03	.23	5.74	.00
4	(constant)	-.72	.08		-8.70	.00
	Interacción	.40	.04	.42	8.84	.00
	restriction	.19	.02	.29	7.32	.00
	interconcepts	.44	.05	.48	7.59	.00
	concepts	-.24	.04	-.30	-4.98	.00

Note: a) DV: “group”.

Father Prior to the overall statistical calculation, the categories were calculated statistically. Each category was weighted by the number of factors included, associated with the respective

percentile, in order to identify whether there was a greater degree of meaningfulness in one category or another previously to the final

decision of the diagnostic decision process (see Table 13).

Table 13. Percentiles to the Categories (SD) and Their Corresponding ZS

PERCENTILES	ΣDS-PROCESSING	ΣZS-PROCESSING	ΣDS-SOCIAL	ΣZS-SOCIAL	ΣDS-BEHAVIOUR	ΣZS-BEHAVIOUR
5	5.16	-6.92	1.17	-1.93	.00	-1.97
10	5.16	-6.92	1.50	-1.65	.00	-1.97
15	6.33	-5.76	1.50	-1.65	.00	-1.97
20	8.33	-3.74	1.50	-1.65	.00	-1.97
25	10.33	-2.00	2.00	-1.03	.00	-1.97
30	10.33	-2.00	2.50	-.59	1.50	-.88
35	10.33	-2.00	3.00	-.16	2.50	-.16
40	10.33	-2.00	3.00	-.16	3.00	.19
45	10.33	-2.00	3.00	-.16	3.00	.19
50	10.66	-1.69	3.00	-.16	3.00	.19
55	12.33	.00	3.00	-.16	3.00	.19
60	12.66	.18	3.00	-.16	3.00	.19
65	14.59	2.13	3.00	-.16	3.00	.19
70	15.50	2.91	3.00	-.16	4.00	.91
75	15.87	3.34	3.50	.27	4.00	.91
80	16.66	3.93	4.50	1.32	4.50	1.27
85	19.66	6.95	5.47	2.35	5.00	1.63
90	20.66	7.83	6.00	2.81	6.00	2.36
95	20.66	7.83	6.00	2.81	6.00	2.36
100	20.66	7.83	6.00	2.81	6.00	2.36

Note: *ZS-PROCESSING: $z(\text{concepts}) + z(\text{meanings}) + z(\text{hierarchisation}) + z(\text{interconcepts}) + z(\text{nodes}) + z(\text{retrieval})/6$; ZS-SOCIAL: $z(\text{interaction}) + z(\text{communication})/2$; ZS-BEHAVIOUR: $z(\text{stereotypies}) + z(\text{restriction})/2$.

Finally, it's now possible to delimit the final diagnostic with high reliability, getting the typical score found to line up with the corresponding percentile (see Table 14).

Table 14. ZS-TOTAL

PERCENTILES	SD- TOTAL	ZS- TOTAL
5	8.00	-9.23
10	9.70	-8.02
15	10.10	-7.81
20	14.00	-3.91
25	15.77	-3.69
30	16.38	-2.55
35	18.20	-2.10
40	18.20	-2.10
45	18.20	-2.10
50	19.20	-1.38

55	20.00	.07
60	20.40	.60
65	23.20	.88
70	26.20	2.79
75	26.20	3.84
80	28.20	4.83
85	32.15	8.64
90	34.67	10.59
100	36.20	11.43

Diagnostic

Selecting the corresponding ZS score for each category and its related percentile (from Table 13), which allowed for an inter-category comparison in relation to the total diagnosis observed in the final section (see Table 15).

Table 15. Diagnostic

It's possible to do this process with the Processing category:		
	ZS	P
I. Processing		
Thus, perform the same operation for the Social Category:		
	ZS	P
II. Social		
The same ZS score sum for Behaviour Category:		
	ZS	P
III. Behaviour		

Total Scores

The closest percentile found in the summary in Table 14 is adjusted, which gives the final percentile to ASD' diagnose (see Table 16).

Table 16. Final Diagnostic*

$\Sigma_{ZS(TOTAL)}$	P**

Note: *Final percentil: See Table TOTAL SCORE in Table 14; **The base percentile, from which ASD is diagnosed, ranges from 50-55 (-1.38-.07). As the percentile increased, so does the severity of the ASD' diagnosis.

Discussion

The descriptive analysis of the factors, regarding to the 'group' variable, found through the one-way ANOVA test, has shown that there're significant differences for all factors (sig: .00). Meanwhile, the same comparative study for the variable 'gender' showed different results, with significant critical levels for the factors 'concepts' (sig: .01), 'interconcepts' (sig: .00) and 'recovery' (sig: .00); however, no significant differences were found in all other factors of the study to the 'gender' variable. Finally, with regard to the variable 'age', significant differences were found for all age intervals for all study factors.

Afterwards, the SD were transformed into standard scores, since each standard score expresses the number of standard deviations and their distance from each value with relation to their own mean, which gives a better reference point for describing the distribution of the

sample data collected than the SD means themselves. Firstly, this was done for the 'group' variable and, subsequently, the general ZS typical values for the whole set of SD of all the study factors, which finally determine the ASD' specific diagnosis.

The predictability of the factors gathered was assessed through a stepwise linear regression analysis for all the study factors, which identified four highly significant predictor variables corresponding to four significant explanatory steps of regression model. The first step is formed by 'interaction' factor (social category), the stp second by the 'restriction' factor (behavioural category), and the third and fourth steps are made up of two factors corresponding to the processing category: 'interconcepts' and 'concepts'.

Based on the study factors, the three study categories have been calculated: 1) processing, which is the average weighted sum of the factors 'concepts', 'meaning', 'hierarchisation', 'interconcepts', "nodes" and 'retrieval'; 2) social, formed by the weighted average sum of two factors: 'interaction' and 'social communication'; and 3) behaviour, formed by the weighted average sum of also two factors: "stereotypies" and 'restriction'. The ZS summary for the three categories allowed to find the final average total summary (μ), which determined the diagnostic level of the autistic disorder, whose average reference value is based from the 50th percentile (Z: -1.38). From the 50th percentile, the level of disorder increased with the rising total typical score observed. In broad terms, mild autism is classified as being between the 50th and 65th percentile, which becomes significantly more severe between the 70th and 80th percentile and, finally, would correspond to severe autism when

it's between the 85th and 100th percentile; However, on a general level, these levels are subject to other factors, such as the type of categorical dimension most affected, the presence of other comorbidities associated with the disorder, or other environmental features, which could severely complicate symptomatic groups and affect the pathway of neurological processing connectivity.

Throughout the whole process described in the information processing circuit, the factors making up the three categories don't interact independently, but form a systemic whole that's inseparable when it needs to figure out the specific symptom group. That is, the social component explains the first procedural step, which is going to have a specific influence on the source memory, which make up the initial contextual processing for the self-other relationship, which will subsequently influence the creation of episodic memory. Then, subsequently, if working memory allows access to semantic memory, contextual episodic memory will enable the retrieval of semantic information in accordance with the required context. If this is not so, that is, if episodic memory has not been formed in the initial perceptual setting, the semantic category could be done accessed incorrectly when an action is required in the environment. Specifically, for this reason, people with ASD often react inappropriately to demands from the environment, even though they have accumulated information regarding that same knowledge or action requested.

Thus, deficits in source and episodic memory, as well as semantic memory, are linked to deficits in the process of neural connectivity as a whole, focused on more or less persistent alterations in the medial temporal lobe, as well as in other neural mechanisms of the GABA-A neuroreceptor, that is, in the set of frontal and parietal cortical structures that makeup the connectivity of the neuropsychological system of information processing, all of which, as a whole, form a systemic set of actions.

In people with ASD, the systemic circuit points to their greatest limitation or obstruction in source memory or contextual-episodic memory,

that is, the action produced at the initial stage of learning, which involved the self-other relationship. This affects the semantically-based networks in a systemic way and, consequently, all cognitive executive functions, which, in turn, modulate semantic representations or the meanings of concepts and, above all, the conceptual interrelation.

Logically, this semantic control is most necessary when representations have been encoded more weakly and locally, resulting in greater dependence on the initial learning context, e.g., a research showed how the presentation of concepts associated with a particular colour, expressive video or social context, well related to the incoming information, enhanced it and made it easier for the source memory to capture much more features of the concept, compared to other situations where the stimulus or information was initially presented in a unimodal way, which hindered the working memory's ability to perform its continuous processing action.

Once the information has gone through the information circuit and entered into the permanent memory, it is transformed into timeless knowledge, the depth of which will vary depending on the type of teaching-learning received. Therefore, when learning is multimodal, auditory, visual, and interactive, the concept of learning acquires greater depth, whereas, on the contrary, if it was taught exclusively through an expository and individual methodology, its level of depth is significantly lower. Therefore, the greatest explanatory variance for the strengthening of concepts at the semantic level is the deepening of multidimensional relationships, which have been developed through nodes or relational links during the initial learning process itself.

For this reason, it's not possible to separate the three dimensions or categories of the neuroprocessing system: social, behavioural, and cognitive processing, as this would reduce the empirical validity of the diagnostic group that shapes ASD.

This could reduce the high percentage of diagnostic errors that currently exist, not justly because the three dimensions are intrinsically related, but also because of the incidence of

explanatory variance between the categories, such as the three form an unseparable group in the ASD' diagnostic process.

Conclusion

Recent years, research has focused on presenting empirical studies that analyze neural connectivity of information as a key element of neuroprocessing in individuals with ASD, with the main aim of explaining the symptom groups identified by official classifications; but, secondly, these studies have revealed other nuclear symptoms that may form the diagnostic group in the same way as social and behavioural dimensions (APA, 2013, *op. cit.*; Friston, 2000; Honey et al., 2009; Horwitz & Glabus, 2005).

Psychological and medical tests of various kinds have been used in these studies. Techniques based on magnetic resonance imaging, including diffusion tensor imaging, have been used to examine the structural integrity of white matter tracts, which are considered to be the macrostructural correlates of brain connectivity (Behrens et al., 2003; Fields, 2008; Karlsgodt et al., 2008; Oishi et al., 2008). Tractography has also been used, which can be applied to trace fibrous tracts, allowing for in vivo mapping of the connectional association pathways of fibres and, although these techniques still present two issues, the main one being their ability to deal with the many different fibre orientations within a same voxel (Hagmann et al., 2003; Hagmann et al., 2008; Lewis et al., 2009; Wedeen et al., 2008); Furthermore, these data could offer a somewhat simplistic view of connective action without being studied intrinsically in connection with the systemic neuroprocessing of information (Karadottir et al., 2008; Schummers et al., 2008; Ziskin et al., 2007).

Structural magnetic resonance imaging has also been used to analyse correlations between the size of different brain regions. (Boucher et al., 2005), As well as this, different techniques have been deployed to facilitate the localisation of initial structural magnetic resonance imaging data, including voxel-based morphometry to understand the process involved in the ASD' formation (Abell et al., 1999).

But the connective process isn't a linear system; it's got multiple interactive pathways. In this respect, long-distance subconnectivity in people with ASD implies that any facet of psychological function that involves coordination or integration of brain regions, is susceptible to disruption, particularly when the computational demand for coordination is more complex (Just et al., 2004; Just et al, 2007), it's interrelated with the main deficits of this disorder, as social interaction, language, and repetitive and restrictive behaviours. (Herbert, 2005; Lewis & Elman, 2008; Mottron et al., 2006).

Therefore, from this viewpoint, many of the explanatory components of the Theory of Central Cognitive Coherence cannot be rejected (Happé, 1999; Happé & Frith, 2006), who suggested that people with ASD have a cognitive style that's focused on processing information very localised way, instead of perceiving a global information way; this has been refuted by Just et al. (2004), who pointed out that Central Coherence Theory hypothesizes a global-central deficit in information processing. Furthermore, local hyperconnectivity has also been linked to findings of behavioural hyper-specificity and inferior generalisation in students with ASD (Casanova et al., 2006; Cohen, 2007; McClelland, 2000), with a high degree of higher discrimination in certain specific tasks (Cohen, 2007; Mottron et al., 2006), as, e.g., demonstrated by the studies of the encrusted figures (Plaisted, O' Riordan & Baron-Cohen, 1998; Shah & Frith, 1983).

Within this systemic process, the cerebellum is viewed as a co-processor of general information processing, able to influence wide-ranging functions through its connectivity with the cerebral cortex (D'Angelo y Casali, 2012; Ito, 2008; Kana et al., 2011; Maximo et al., 2014; Van Overwalle & Mariën, 2016). Indeed, on this subject, a new and interesting area of research has focused on cerebellar-cerebral functional connectivity, which involved how the cerebellum connects differentially with higher-order cognitive regions and cortical networks, in which individuals with ASD showed alterations in specific connections between the cerebellum and the cortex (D'Mello & Stoodley, 2015; Mosconi et al., 2015).

Currently, research has demonstrated the direct connectivity between the cerebellum and regions of the cerebral cortex, employing functional magnetic resonance imaging in a non-active state (Igelström et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2015; Oldehinkel et al., 2019; Olivito et al., 2016, *op.cit.*; Olivito et al., 2017, *op.cit.*). Specifically, this study found that the cerebellum was hyperconnected with sensorimotor regions of the cortex and hypoconnected with supramodal regions. Furthermore, among individuals with ASD, there're greater connections between the supramodal regions of the cerebellum and the sensorimotor regions of the cortex and conversely.

Igelström et al. (2017) divided the temporoparietal union, an important region for social cognition, into 11 subdivisions through independent component analysis, were applied to examine functional connectivity with cerebellar voxels, and a decrease in functional connectivity was observed in individuals with ASD.

In overall, most studies have observed a decrease in connectivity between the cerebellum and cortical regions that contribute to higher-order supramodal functions, However, the strongest argument in support of local hyperconnectivity might come from the micro level, where some irregularities in hyperconnectivity reports within mid-range thalamocortical networks have been analysed, as well as converging evidence, suggesting that disruptions to and from the frontal and temporal areas of the cortex might be more severely affected in this disorder.

These findings are coherent with the idea that relatively intact early development and is progressively affected throughout the first years of life, as short-range connectivity increases and long-range connectivity is reduced. (Herbert et al., 2005; Johnson, 2005; Pardo & Eberhart, 2007; Redcay & Courchesne, 2005).

The wide breadth of these studies focused on connectivity has revealed the presence of microstructural differences between people with ASD and people with other kinds of disorders. This means the connectional process of the neuroprocessual information system, which affects multiple structural components, is a

systemic group that cannot be ignored in ASD' currently diagnostic processes (Greicius, 2008).

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